

Statistical Periodicity in Classical and Quantum Physics

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It is known in the literature that there exists a strong link between quantum mechanics (e.g. a particle in a box with an infinite potential at the walls) and standing sound waves as described in (1) (or even waves on a string). This relationship goes beyond the sinusoidal solutions and includes interference and other features discussed in (1). In (2), we suggest that periodicity in both classical and quantum solutions may be based on the statistical idea of maximum entropy. For example, a particle in a classical gas with no potential has equal probability to be at any point x . If one wishes to retain this idea of equal probability at each x , yet have momentum linked to x , then $\exp(ipx)$ is a solution which allows for this. It has a modulus of one and is also periodic in space which is the “next best thing” to being constant. In classical statistical mechanics (3), the Boltzmann transport equation allows one to find a density which describes sound in a medium. In this note, we examine the various assumptions used to derive this wave-equation and investigate whether one may anticipate this periodicity at a stage in the derivation prior to the sound wave equation being derived. We argue that a periodic solution may be part of a more general statistical idea of maximum entropy.

Sound Waves and Quantum Mechanics

Sound waves are traditionally described by the equation:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} (\text{partial}) \text{ density} + cc \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} (\text{partial}) \text{ density} = 0 \quad ((1))$$

with c being the speed of sound. This equation is a well-known wave equation, yet depends on quite a few assumptions if derived from the Boltzmann transport equation as done in ((3)). If one separates density into pure time and space factors, :

$$\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \text{density} (\text{space}) (x) + b \text{density} (\text{space}) (x) = 0 \quad ((2))$$

which leads to a sinusoidal type solution.

The time-independent Schrodinger equation for a particle in a box is of the same form as ((2)) as is the Helmholtz equation in electromagnetism. This leads to the question: Is it possible these periodic solutions follow from a statistical maximization of entropy i.e. from a process which attempts to make x space isotropic as much as possible while allowing for dynamical changes?

For quantum mechanics, we argue that for a free particle:

$$\frac{d}{dx} \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \quad ((3))$$

$\exp(ipx)$ is the relative conditional probability. We suggested ((3)) may be more general:

$$W(x+dx) = W(x) \exp(i (-i d/dx \ln W)) \quad ((4))$$

Here $\langle \text{momentum conditional} \rangle = -i d/dx \ln W$. Thus, the average conditional momentum governs the spatial change in the wavefunction $W(x)$ and leads to a pattern of humps which are “almost periodic”. We have suggested in previous notes that this occurs because $\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle$ is a periodic function itself. We wish to see if similar ideas hold in the classical statistical mechanics situation.

Classical Statistical Mechanics and the Sound Wavefunction

In (3), a conservation theorem is developed based on the Boltzmann transport equation:

$$\text{Integral } d^3p \ X \ [d/dt (\text{partial}) + v.d/dx + F d/dp] f(r,p,t) = 0 \quad ((5))$$

Here X is a conserved quantity in a collision and F force. $\text{Integral } d^3r f(r,p,t)$ =spatial density n .

It follows from ((5)) that:

$$d/dt (\text{partial}) \langle n X \rangle + d/dx_i \langle n v_i X \rangle - n \langle v_i dX/dx_i \rangle - n/m \langle F_i dX/dv_i \rangle - n/m \langle dF_i/dv_i X \rangle = 0 \quad ((6))$$

Here partial derivatives are used everywhere.

Note: $\langle A \rangle = \text{Integral } d^3p A f(r,p,t) / \text{Integral } d^3p f(r,p,t)$

The approach of (3) used to obtain the sound wave-equation is based on the following ideas. (We later examine these ideas in more detail, but in this section we wish to only obtain the wave equation.)

1. Two conservation equations are obtained, one for $X=1$ and the other for $X=v_j$ the j th component of velocity.
2. It is assumed that $u(r,t) = \text{Integral } d^3p v f(r,p,t) / \text{Integral } d^3p f(r,p,t)$ is small as are partial time and space derivatives of both $u(r,t)$ and $n(r,t)$. $n(r,t)$, however, is not considered to be small. This is an important assumption, because it means that if one takes a derivative of any product of $u(r,t)n(r,t)$, $n(r,t)$ factors like a constant to create a leading order term.
3. Gradient pressure is assumed to be $cc \text{ grad } n(r,t)$ with cc being the speed of sound squared. It is related to the adiabatic compressibility.

Assumptions 1 and 2 lead to the two equations given in (3):

$$\frac{dn(r,t)}{dt} + n \text{ grad. } U = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad n(r,t) \frac{du}{dt} + \text{grad}P = 0 \quad ((6))$$

Taking d/dt of the first and d/dx of the second and noting that $d/dt (n \text{ grad } u) = n d/dt \text{ grad}(u)$ to leading order together with the third assumption, one obtains:

$$\text{Grad. grad } n - n \text{ cc } \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} n \quad ((7))$$

$$\text{This leads to a separable solution of: } n(r,t) = \cos(at) \cos(bt) \quad ((8))$$

Assumptions Used to Derive the Classical Sound Wave Equation

In this note, we are interested in whether one may anticipate ((8)) at an early stage in the above derivation from (3). We first examine the form of ((5)). It appears there is a distinct symmetry as v , velocity, appears in the second term associated with d/dx partial. Thus, using $X=1$ in one equation yields a term with $d/dx (u n)$ while using $X=v$ leads a term with $d/dt (u n)$. In both cases, n factors out like a constant due to the assumption that n is not small, but its derivatives are. As a result, one obtains two equations involving d/dt and d/dx and two variables u and n , of the form:

$$\frac{d}{dt} n + n \frac{d}{dx} u = 0 \quad ((9a)) \quad \text{and} \quad n \frac{d}{dt} u + b \frac{d}{dx} n = 0 \quad ((9b))$$

Here we make the further assumption that $\langle v \cdot v \rangle = b$ i.e. constant in analogy with Pressure = constant times $n(r,t)$ used in (3).

If one examines ((9a)), it seems dn/dt should change in time. If it increases, n being positive, then u decreases in x and vice versa. This, we argue, already suggests periodicity in n in time and forward and backward motion in u (just as there is forward and backward motion in $-i d/dx \ln W$). Furthermore, ((9b)) shows periodicity of $n(r,t)$ in space.

Thus, we argue that the symmetry of ((9a)) and ((9b)), based on the idea that $n(r,t)$ is not small, but u , and derivatives of u and n are, leads to periodicity in $n(r,t)$.

Assuming that $u(r,t)$ is small, however, does not lead explicitly to $u(r,t)$ as a periodic function, rather one obtains a small x,t limit. Examining ((9a)) and ((9b)), one sees that $u = d \cdot x \cdot t$, where d is a constant, is a solution if $n(r,t) = n_1(r) n_2(t)$. Furthermore, n_1 and n_2 are the same function. This suggests that taking $d/dt n_1(t)$ for low t is the same as n times $d \cdot t$. This is exactly the property of $\cos(bt)$ and $\sin(bt)$ for t small. Thus, using small t and x limits, yields low t and x limits of $\cos(at)\cos(bx)$ as a solution for $n(x,t)$. As argued above, however, the periodicity is already present in the form of ((9a)) and ((9b)), but these contain two important assumptions:

1. $\langle v \cdot v \rangle = \text{constant}$ (which is not really true, but is the same assumption made in (3)).
2. $d/dx (nu) = n d/dxu$ or $d/dt (nu) = n d/dt u$.

It seems unusual that one must force u and derivatives of $n(r,t)$ and $u(r,t)$ to be small in order to obtain the sound wave equation. We argue that the periodic solution is really tied to the form of $d/dt = d/dt \text{ partial} + v d/dx + F/dp$. For $F=0$, the last term disappears.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that the periodic solution of sound waves in a classical gas (e.g. pipe with certain boundary conditions), waves on a string, and the quantum solution of a particle in a box with an infinite potential may be based on a general statistical idea that one must have dynamics, yet try to keep the same probability at all points in space as much as possible. It seems that a periodic solution accomplishes this goal. Traditionally, classical waves are derived using a force or pressure related equation which is good, but we also argue the solution should follow from statistics and maximum entropy. In this note, we try to examine the assumptions used to develop the sound wave equation from the Boltzmann transport equation in (3) and argue that it seems to follow from the symmetry of $d/dt = d/dt \text{ partial} + v d/dx$ (with $F=0$) if one assumes that $u = \langle v \rangle$ and derivatives of u and density are small, but density is not. Thus, density behaves to first order as a constant in conservation equations formed with the Boltzmann transport operator. Furthermore, $\langle v_i v_j \rangle$ is set equal to a constant to further exploit this symmetry and lead to periodic motion. We find that $u = \text{constant} \times t$ for small x and t or $\sin(at)\sin(bt)$ in general is periodic (moving back and forth) just like $-i d/dx \ln W$ in quantum mechanics. It is this back and forth motion which creates humps in quantum mechanics and probably plays a similar role in the statistical mechanics of sound.

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